

ISic1629

Epitaph of Ienaris son of Primos

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ἐνθ[ά]δε κεῖτε Ἴε
2. ναρίς υἱὸς Πρίμου
3. τελευτᾷ τῆ̃ πρὸ θ' καλ (ανδῶν)
4. Ἀπριλίῳν ζήσ (ας) ἔτη η'
5. μὴν (ης) ς' κεῖτε μετὰ
6. τῆς μάμη [ς]

Apparatus

Text of Agnello 1953

Translation (it)

Qui giace Ienaris figlio di Priamos. Egli è morto prima delle Calende di Aprile, all'età di 9 anni e

6 mesi. Giace accanto a (sua) madre

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645080

Bibliography

Agnello, S.L. 1953. Silloge di iscrizioni paleocristiane della Sicilia. Rome. At no.61
Libertini, G 1931. Miscellanea epigrafica. *Archivio Storico per la Sicilia Orientale*.
27: 39-53. At 44 no.7

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